

Non-conventional Glass fiber NCF composites with thermoset and thermoplastic matrices.

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ABSTRACT

1 Introduction

The wind industry has achieved undeniable advances over the past few decades. In this context, the composite materials are playing a key role in the development of lightweight, safe and cost-efficient wind turbines. For this purpose, designers need reliable experimental data, in particular in terms of elastic and strength properties, fatigue lifetime as well as aging effects. Moreover, Non Crimp Fabrics (NCF) are widely used in the manufacturing of wind turbine blades. These fabrics consist of unidirectional (UD) fiber layers that are stitched together. They are alternatives to the unidirectional and woven plies and they offer potential advantages for manufacturing. Some research works showed that the in-plane properties of NCF composites could be slightly enhanced in comparison to the woven composites [1, 2], particularly for compression loading. In addition, it is reported that the structural stitching have a beneficial effect on the out of plane properties [3, 4]. Yet, it is worth to note that damage modes are also affected by stitching. It was observed that some features of the NCF's mesostructure lead to early damage initiation (stitching sites, fiber-free zones, etc.) [5, 6].

Non crimp fabrics could also offer more design flexibility with the use of repeated sub-laminate [7], particularly with shallow angled plies. In [8] authors argued that these non conventional NCF composites can offer substantial mass reduction along with performance increase. We propose in this paper a preliminary experimental study on the mechanical behavior of glass NCF composites with shallow angled plies.

Our approach consists in three main steps. First, we investigated the mechanical behavior of the neat resins. We considered a thermoset (epoxy-based) and a thermoplastic (acrylic-based) polymers that are both used in wind industry. They display quite similar physical and mechanical properties. The two following steps aimed at characterizing the laminated composites, quasi-UD and NCF composites respectively, manufactured by vacuum infusion process. We first performed mechanical tests on the quasi-UD laminate to determine the stiffness matrices and the strengths. Finally, we assessed the mechanical behavior of conventional as well as shallow angled NCF composites. The conventional laminated composites were prepared using [0 45 -45] triaxial glass fabrics, while the second type was based on triaxial glass fabrics with the following orientations [0 25 -25] and [0 35 -35].

2 Material

2.1 Non-crimp glass fabrics

The fabrics under investigation are listed in Table. 1. They are produced by Chomarat Group for Infusion or RTM processes. The fiber sizing is designed for epoxy matrices. Each layer is reinforced with 5% of low tex polyester yarn (weft). The ply noted G-0 represents the reference ply. In addition, we consider three tri-axial non crimp fabrics with conventional plies (45°) and shallow angled plies (35° , 25°).

It is worth noting that the stitching is rigorously the same for all non crimp fabrics. We used a hybrid chain tricot stitching with 3,8 mm spacing distance. For the tri-axial fabrics, the off-axis layers have the same weight (about 300 g.m^{-2}).

Reference	Orientation	Areal density (g.m^{-2})	Stitching pattern
G-0	[0]	565	–
G-TX-25	[0_2 25 -25]	1180	Chain Tricot 3.8mm
G-TX-35	[0_2 35 -35]	1195	Chain Tricot 3.8mm
G-TX-45	[0_2 45 -45]	1165	Chain Tricot 3.8mm

Table 1: Conventional and shallow angled glass non-crimp fabrics (Chomarat Company).

2.2 Matrices

We consider in this study two polymeric matrices that are both used in manufacturing of wind turbine blades:

- The thermoset matrix is the Epolam 2040 developed by Axson Technologies company. It is a commercially available epoxy system that is mainly based on a Bisphenol A epichlorohydrin resin. It was cured with an amine hardener (Epolam 2047). Selected properties are given in Table 2.
- The second type of polymer matrix is the newly developed Elium resin by Arkema company. It is a liquid acrylic-based thermoplastic matrix (used with an initiator).

These two matrices display a quite similar mechanical behaviour. Yet, we should highlight few differences. First, the tensile strength of the thermoplastic matrix is lower in comparison to the thermoset one. This difference should impact the damage behaviour of the laminate, particularly for matrix-dominated modes. The second difference is a consequence of the nature of the matrices. Indeed, the thermoplastic matrix has major advantages regarding manufacturing and end of life treatment.

Matrix	Glass transition temperature	Elastic modulus	Ultimate tensile strength
Thermoset	90 °C	2.9 GPa	71 MPa
Thermoplastic	NC	3 GPa	58 MPa

Table 2: Selected properties of the matrices under study.

2.3 Processing

The composite plates were manufactured by the vacuum infusion technique. We used a classical setup to drive the resin into the laminate. As prepared plates were 400 mm by 400 mm.

We need to distinguish between the processing of the epoxy-based laminates and the acrylic-based ones. The curing of the thermoset based composite plates was completed after a two-step process. The temperature was first kept 6 hours at ambient and then post-cured at 50°C during 24 hours. On the contrary, the curing of the thermoplastic composite is completed after 6 hours at ambient (Table. 3).

The total volume fiber fraction (v_f) and the void content (v_v) were determined by matrix carbonization according to the standard ASTM D3171. The volume fiber fraction in the yarn direction is estimated at $46,5\% \pm 1$. The average void content is estimated at 7%.

Table 3: Processing of the composite plates.

Matrix	Process	Curing	Post-curing
Thermoset	Vacuum Infusion	6H at 25°C	24H at 50°C
Thermoplastic	Vacuum Infusion	6H at 25°C	–

Figure 1: Optical micrographs of the microstructure of the thermoplastic based UD laminate.

3 Experiment

The mechanical tests were conducted under quasi static conditions, with an imposed displacement speed of 1mm/min. For each stacking sequence, three specimens were instrumented with a tee-type strain gage (longitudinal and transverse directions), and a mechanical extensometer on the other face. For the unidirectional laminate, we performed tensile tests on specimens with the following orientations: 0°, 90° and 45°.

Figures 3 to 5 display stress strain relations ($\sigma - \varepsilon$) for the unirectionnall laminates as well as for NCF composites.

Figure 2: Optical micrographs of the microstructure of the thermoset based UD laminate.

(a) Thermoplastic matrix (TP)

(b) Thermoset matrix (TS)

Figure 3: Stress-strain relations for the unidirectional laminates under uniaxial tensile test in the fiber direction (0°).

(a) Transverse direction (90°)

(b) At 45°

Figure 4: Stress-strain relations for the unidirectional laminates under uniaxial tensile test in the transverse direction (90°) and at 45°.

Figure 5: Stress-strain relations for the NCF composite laminates under uniaxial tensile test.

4 Results

4.1 Properties of the plies

Table 4 summarizes the main mechanical characteristics that were derived from the tensile tests of the unidirectional laminate. E_x , E_y and E_s are the longitudinal, transverse and shear elastic moduli respectively. ν_x is the Poisson's ratio. ε_X^* and ε_Y^* are the strains to failure in the fiber and transverse directions respectively. X and Y are the tensile strengths in the fiber and transverse directions respectively. ε_S^* and S are the strain to failure and the strength under shear loading, as determined for the 45° specimens. Care should be taken regarding the failure data under shear loading.

Matrix	E_x	E_y	E_s	ν_x	ε_X^*	ε_Y^*	ε_S^*	X	Y	S
	GPa	GPa	GPa		%	%	%			
Thermoset	40.3	14.1	6.4	0.245	2.45 ^a	1.7	1.27	860 ^a	64	49
Thermoplastic	39.5	12.6	4.9	0.22	2.58 ^a	1.8	2	858 ^a	58	49.7

Table 4: Mechanical characteristics that were derived from the tensile tests of the unidirectional laminate.

4.2 Effect of the nature of the matrix

Table. 4 shows that the nature of the matrix has an effect on the transverse and shear elastic properties. As expected, it has almost no effect on the fiber direction, which is mainly driven by the fiber content. We should note that the ultimate tensile strength in the transverse direction is lower than it is for the thermoplastic based composite.

Table. 5 shows the tensile properties of conventional NCF composites with both matrices (thermoset, thermoplastic). The elastic modulus in the longitudinal direction (0°), E_1 , is compared to the one that is predicted by the classical laminate theory, based on the ply properties given in Table. 4. The strain to failure and the ultimate strength are also given in Table. 5.

Matrix	Stacking sequence	E_1 (GPa)		ε_1^* (%)	σ_1^* (MPa)
		Experimental	Computed (CLT)		
Thermoset	$[0_2 45 -45]_2$	29.3	29.4	2	452
Thermoplastic	$[0_2 45 -45]_2$	26.9	27.3	2.3	480

Table 5: Mechanical characteristics that were derived from the tensile tests of the conventional NCF composites.

4.3 Effect of shallow angles

The use of shallow angled plies would have a beneficial effect on the longitudinal direction (E_1). Yet, it would also lead to a decrease in the transverse and shear properties. Table. 6 indicates the relative changes in the stiffness matrix components of the non conventional NCF composites, in comparison with the conventional one ($[0_2, 45, -45]$), as predicted by the classical laminate theory. Table. 7 shows the tensile properties of the NCF composites with conventional and shallow angled plies. The experimental results are qualitatively in good agreement with the predictions. Yet, we should highlight some differences between the experimental longitudinal tensile modulus, E_1 , and the prediction, particularly for the non conventional NCF.

Matrix	Stacking sequence	E ₁	E ₂	E ₆	ν_{12}
Thermoplastic	[0 ₂ 25 -25] ₂	+23,7%	-15,5%	-17,1%	-5,4%
Thermoplastic	[0 ₂ 35 -35] ₂	+9,8%	-10,8%	-4,8%	+6,2%

Table 6: Predicted stiffness matrix components (classical laminate theory) of non conventional NCF composites (the reference being the [0₂ 45 -45]₂ laminate).

Matrix	Stacking sequence	E ₁ (GPa)		ε_1^* (%)	σ_1^* (MPa)
		Experimental	Computed (CLT)		
Thermoplastic	[0 ₂ 25 -25] ₂	29.3	33.9	2.11	508
Thermoplastic	[0 ₂ 35 -35] ₂	27.3	30.1	2.25	455
Thermoplastic	[0 ₂ 45 -45] ₂	26.9	27.4	2.3	480

Table 7: Mechanical characteristics that were derived from the tensile tests of the thermoplastic based NCF composites.

5 Conclusion

We studied the static mechanical behavior of non crimp fabric composites. Two aspects were specifically investigated: the use of (1) a liquid thermoplastic matrix and (2) the shallow angled plies.

We showed that the thermoplastic-based composites exhibit quite similar behavior to that of thermoset ones. Yet, some features in these preliminary results indicate that damage initiate earlier in the case of thermoplastic composites.

Also, the use of shallow angled plies is an alternative to the conventional NCF composites. We showed that the elastic properties of non conventional NCF differ slightly from the predictions of the classical laminate theory.

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